

Towards More Effective Data Visualisation of Health Inequalities: Key Research Questions

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Summary

Reducing health inequalities in the UK requires public and policymaker support for policies concerning the wider determinants of health. Cartography and data visualisation can be useful tools for advocates to communicate evidence persuasively, but poor design can stigmatise vulnerable groups. This paper identifies key research questions that remain unanswered for public health advocates wishing to maximise the impact of data visualisations while minimising their harms. The questions are intended to inform extensive user testing, and are drawn from the literature on data visualisation and health communication.

KEYWORDS: health inequalities; data visualisation; wider determinants of health; visualisation rhetoric

Introduction

In response to a failure in UK policy to reduce persistent health and social inequalities (along a range of dimensions), there are increasing calls for public health advocates to present evidence more effectively and engage the public (Smith and Garthwaite, 2015). These actors can improve public and policymaker support for relevant policies by framing their messages – considering what to emphasise or leave unsaid and how to explain an issue (L'Hôte *et al.*, 2022). Framing applies not only to written communications, but also to data visualisations, in which editorial decisions are necessarily made at several layers (Hullman and Diakopoulos, 2011). This paper draws on that framework to identify unanswered questions on how public health advocates can maximise the impact of data visualisation while minimising its harms.

Data visualisations serve several purposes in a public health context. They are used during data analysis to see patterns, check data quality, and assist with methodological choices (Ruddle *et al.*, 2023). Governments utilise data visualisations in public health messaging to facilitate behaviour change. Clinicians may present risk information to patients using charts. Finally, researchers, the media and other actors may publish visualisations for public and policy audiences that show the extent of inequalities, its associated factors, or its potential solutions. These may be used to raise awareness, to assist with the allocation of resources, or to advocate for policy change. The questions identified in this paper are concerned with this last set of use cases.

Challenges communicating health inequalities

While research on health inequalities has grown exponentially over the last 50 years (Cash-Gibson *et al.*, 2018), these inequalities have widened, reflecting a failure in policy (Marmot, 2024). This is visualised for 1982-2015 in **Figure 1**. According to Mackenbach (2011), this is partly a communication problem; large-scale policy reform requires an improved public understanding of the severity, causes,

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and solutions to the issue.

Figure 1 Research on health inequalities from high-income countries has grown exponentially while health inequalities between social classes in England and Wales have persisted, 1984-2014.

Public understanding of health inequalities, while nuanced, places responsibility disproportionately on individual behaviours rather than the wider determinants of health (L'Hôte *et al.*, 2018). Message framing affects how people apportion individual vs external responsibility for various issues including health and its wider determinants (Niederdeppe *et al.*, 2011). A shift away from blaming individual behaviours would affect policy preferences (L'Hôte *et al.*, 2022), and may also reduce stigma. The stigmatisation of people and – in a context of geographical health inequalities – places can widen health inequalities through psychosocial pathways and employment opportunities.

Data visualisation in a health inequalities context

Data visualisation is one tool available to public health advocates that can engage and persuade audiences. D'Ignazio and Klein (2020) note that cartographers have long recognised that even small design changes in maps influence user takeaways. Hullman and Diakopoulos (2011, p. 2232) describe how “a rhetorical dimension is present in every design”. In their analytical framework of *visualisation rhetoric*, they identify four layers at which editorial decisions are made: “the data, visual representation, textual annotations, and interactivity”. Design choices at each of these layers are increasingly the subject of research experiments, but they are usually measured against user comprehension or memorability (Gubala and Melonçon, 2022).

In a health inequalities context with well-documented communication challenges, other user responses should be considered. Firstly, the failure of evidence to drive policy change means that data visualisations should not only inform, but also persuade audiences. Secondly, since public and policy discussions focus disproportionately on individual behaviours rather than the wider determinants of health, visualisations of aggregated data should not reinforce individualistic thinking or stigmatise vulnerable groups. Thirdly, visualisations should convey the credibility of the measure or the statistical analysis, which audiences can doubt in highly political contexts.

Best practices may be optimised by assessing how design changes (such as those that form part of the *visualisation rhetoric* framework) affect policy preferences, individualistic thinking, and perceived credibility. A list of those questions are shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Practical questions about data visualisation for public health advocates

Editorial layer (from the <i>visualisation rhetoric</i> framework)	Design Element	Research Question
Data	Uncertainty	<p>Does visualising uncertainty lead to greater user trust of (inherently political) health inequalities messaging?</p> <p>Is there necessarily a trade-off between visualising uncertainty and conveying a clear message?</p>
	Aggregation of social groups	Does disaggregating groups (for example, breaking down ethnicities into more granular ethnic groups) reduce feelings of marginalisation? Does it come at the cost of a clear visualisation?
	Absolute vs relative measures	Does using absolute or relative measures of health inequalities influence policy preferences, credibility, or empathetic responses?
	Variance (presence/absence)	Visualising within-group dispersion of health outcomes, rather than means alone, reduces blaming individuals for inequalities (Holder and Xiong, 2022). Does this, in turn, increase support for policies targeting the wider determinants of health?
Visual representation	Variance (type of display)	Motivated by the same rationale as the question above, do different representations of variance (for example, confidence intervals vs jitter plots) affect policy preference?
	Animated vs static	Are animated graphics more persuasive, or have an impact on the perceived credibility?
Annotation	Photographs	Do photographs (for example, of individuals or places) within data visualisations influence policy preferences, credibility, or empathetic responses?
	Illustrative quotes	Do illustrative quotes within data visualisations influence policy preferences, credibility, or empathetic responses?
	Text placement	Given the importance of annotation (Stokes <i>et al.</i> , 2023) and that graphics are often shared without the original accompanying text, are narratives more effective for persuasion when presented <i>within</i> or <i>alongside</i> a data visualisation?
Interactivity	Scaling; filtering; label identification (mouseover)	Does the use of various interactive techniques impact persuasion, credibility, or empathetic responses? Does it come at the cost of a clear story?
	Prediction (user sketching)	If users are asked to predict patterns before seeing them, do the data visualisations prove more persuasive, credible, or induce empathy?

These questions are all pertinent in a health inequalities context because policy support, empathetic responses and statistical credibility are useful goals in health communication. Moreover, some of the design elements are particularly relevant in this context. On uncertainty, Hullman (2020) argues that visualising uncertainty is a rational design decision because it constrains the potentially infinite statistical uncertainty that users can imagine. Indeed, the authors of *The Spirit Level* – a best-selling book advocating for tackling inequality – received substantial criticism for their simple charts because of a perceived lack of statistical rigour (Pickett and Wilkinson, 2015). Yet simpler charts might have a wider appeal and a greater persuasive impact. Hans Rosling described this tension as “[having] to be like the worst tabloid newspaper in the front and the Academy of Science in the back.” (Allen and Cookson, 2014). A better understanding of whether visualising uncertainty necessarily affects user trust or persuasiveness could prove invaluable to public health advocates.

On animation, Tsang (2023) finds that animated climate graphics in the media are perceived as more biased than static graphics, perhaps because it appears as though the journalist is “trying harder”. Is this also the case in the similarly political context of health inequalities? Are they persuasive, nonetheless?

Finally, assessing the impact of illustrative quotes and photographs matter in this context because quantitative data, while invaluable, capture very little of the human experience of health inequalities (Elliott *et al.*, 2015). These design elements may prime more empathetic explanations when shown alongside robust community-based statistics.

Conclusion

This paper has articulated key questions that remain unanswered for public health advocates seeking to maximise the impact of data visualisation and minimise its harms. We will shortly begin survey experiments with the public to test some of these questions, with preliminary results anticipated in the coming months. Previous research suggests that such experiments should consider moderating for preexisting attitudes and chart literacy.

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References

Allen, K. and Cookson, C. (2014) ‘Science: Hans Rosling – data rock star’, *Financial Times*, 17 January. Available at: <https://www.ft.com/content/4c48c81a-7d7b-11e3-a48f-00144feabdc0> (Accessed: 19 January 2024).

Cash-Gibson, L. *et al.* (2018) ‘Inequalities in global health inequalities research: A 50-year bibliometric analysis (1966-2015)’, *PLOS ONE*, 13(1), p. e0191901. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0191901>.

D’Ignazio, C. and Klein, L.F. (2020) *Data Feminism*. Cambridge: MIT Libraries Experimental Collections Fund (Strong Ideas). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11805.001.0001>.

Elliott, E., Popay, J. and Williams, G. (2015) ‘16 - Knowledge of the everyday: Confronting the causes of health inequalities’, in K.E. Smith, C. Bamba, and S.E. Hill (eds) *Health Inequalities: Critical Perspectives*. Oxford University Press, p. 0. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198703358.003.0016>.

Gubala, C. and Melonçon, L. (2022) ‘Data Visualizations: An Integrative Literature Review of Empirical Studies Across Disciplines’, in *2022 IEEE International Professional Communication Conference (ProComm)*. *2022 IEEE International Professional Communication Conference*

(*ProComm*), pp. 112–119. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ProComm53155.2022.00024>.

Holder, E. and Xiong, C. (2022) ‘Dispersion vs Disparity: Hiding Variability Can Encourage Stereotyping When Visualizing Social Outcomes’. arXiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2208.04440>.

Hullman, J. (2020) ‘Why Authors Don’t Visualize Uncertainty’, *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 26(1), pp. 130–139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2019.2934287>.

Hullman, J. and Diakopoulos, N. (2011) ‘Visualization Rhetoric: Framing Effects in Narrative Visualization’, *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 17(12), pp. 2231–2240. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2011.255>.

L’Hôte, E. *et al.* (2022) *A Matter of Life and Death: Explaining the Wider Determinants of Health in the UK*. Frameworks Institute.

L’Hôte, E., Volmert, A. and Fond, M. (2018) *Seeing Upstream: Mapping the Gaps between Expert and Public Understandings of Health in the United Kingdom*. Available at: <https://www.frameworksinstitute.org/publication/seeing-upstream-mapping-the-gaps-between-expert-and-public-understandings-of-health-in-the-united-kingdom/> (Accessed: 27 July 2023).

Mackenbach, J.P. (2011) ‘Can we reduce health inequalities? An analysis of the English strategy (1997–2010)’, *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 65(7), pp. 568–575. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.2010.128280>.

Marmot, M. (2024) ‘We know what we need to do to improve health and reduce inequalities, now we need politicians to act’, *BMJ*, 384, p. q93. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.q93>.

Niederdeppe, J., Shapiro, M.A. and Porticella, N. (2011) ‘Attributions of Responsibility for Obesity: Narrative Communication Reduces Reactive Counterarguing among Liberals’, *Human Communication Research*, 37(3), pp. 295–323. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2958.2011.01409.x>.

Pickett, K. and Wilkinson, R. (2015) ‘20 - The Spirit Level: A case study of the public dissemination of health inequalities research’, in K.E. Smith, C. Bambra, and S.E. Hill (eds) *Health Inequalities: Critical Perspectives*. Oxford University Press, p. 0. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198703358.003.0020>.

Ruddle, R.A., Cheshire, J. and Fernstad, S.J. (2023) ‘Tasks and Visualizations Used for Data Profiling: A Survey and Interview Study’, *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2023.3234337>.

Smith, K. and Garthwaite, K. (2015) ‘6 - Contrasting views on ways forward for health inequalities research’, in K.E. Smith, C. Bambra, and S.E. Hill (eds) *Health Inequalities: Critical Perspectives*. Oxford University Press, p. 0. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198703358.003.0006>.

Stokes, C. *et al.* (2023) ‘Striking a Balance: Reader Takeaways and Preferences when Integrating Text and Charts’, *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 29(1), pp. 1233–1243. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2022.3209383>.

Tsang, S.J. (2023) ‘Communicating Climate Change: The Impact of Animated Data Visualizations on Perceptions of Journalistic Motive and Media Bias’, *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 67(2), pp. 161–182. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08838151.2023.2182788>.

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